

Segmenting Analysis of Brain Disorders

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Abstract

As the world's life expectancy rate falls, the human race's attention is drawn to various health-related concerns. One such disease is Cancer which can be of several types. The human brain is a complex organ that manages the functionality of billions of cells present in the human body; hence it acts as the center of the nervous system. It serves as the commanding officer of the body, and any disorder or health issue related to it can lead to the risk of losing a life. These abnormalities in the brain, such as cancerous cells or tumors, are known as Brain disorders. They usually occur whenever there is a raw and abandoned division of cells or group of cells inside or around the brain. Brain tumors are threatening and deadly as they affect the whole brain and body functionality and may also damage the normal cells of different organs. Therefore, brain disorders must be treated with special care to prevent the loss of human life. There have been considerable advancements in medical science, and advanced technological tools have made it possible to eradicate all such threats to precious human life. This study does a structured literature review of the present situation and conducts a systematic overview of the research on this subject. It analyzes the possible ways to detect the presence, progression, and alter the growth of dangerous tumor cells inside the brain with the help of Neural Networks. The discussion has been done over various techniques (machine learning algorithms, deep learning techniques, segmentation techniques, and image processing methods) to achieve accurate and efficient results, which can help in the early treatment of the patients. The central insight gained is to architect a model using Neural Networks, which can improve the process and make it error-free, smooth, fast, and reliable for detecting and adequately identifying disordered brain regions. Thus, the classification model using the Convolutional Neural Network and segmentation using Edge detection-based segmentation with contour detection give reliable results for detecting any disorders inside the brain.

Keywords: brain disorders, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), machine learning, MRI, tumor detection

1. Introduction

The global population is increasing exponentially, and so is the risk of various health-related problems. Cancer is still one of the deadliest diseases ever, among which Brain cancer still haunts many. Over time, advancements in science and technology have been possible to fight such diseases that threaten to lose a life. The hour needs to incorporate the next-level technologies (like Artificial Intelligence) to develop a system that could study, analyze, and predict the growth of such tumor cells. It can help effectively treat patients diagnosed with Brain tumors and save many people's lives [19-23].

The human brain is the most important as well as the most intricate organ. It is the governing center for the human body as it commands the nervous system. It controls all the activities and actions of the human body, from receiving inputs from receptors to overseeing the effort associated with it. The human brain mainly consists of Cerebrum, Cerebellum, Brainstem, and Cerebrospinal fluid. Each of these parts is equally important for the vital functioning of the brain and thus the body. Any disorder in any of these parts can produce a tremendous effect on the functioning of many aspects of the human body, and if not taken into proper consideration, these disorders can turn into deadly Cancer [4].

With time, crucial technological developments have made it possible to identify the development of such disorders and tumors inside the brain. One such advancement in medical imaging is Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), which provides information about the brain and the associated abnormalities. MRI is mainly of the following types (Figure 1):

- T1 (T1-weighted): Brain tumor borders appear brighter in this.
- T2 (T2-weighted): Fluid retention appears brighter in this.
- FLAIR: It provides a clear distinction between cerebrospinal fluid and fluid retention.

Figure 1: Different forms of MRI

This study mainly aims to analyze the possible ways to detect the presence, progression, and alter the growth of dangerous tumor cells inside the brain with the help of Neural Networks; this will lead to a positive social impact through timely and effective treatment of the patients.

2. Literature Review

In a world of almost 7 billion people, more than 100 million people across the globe suffer from some form of tumor/cancer. It leads to a reduction in life expectancy rates and an increased death rate every year. In this study, we have tried to incorporate technology with medical science to develop a solution for identifying disorders in the brain. Varied literature is studied to gain more information regarding already implemented technologies for detecting brain tumors and other related diseases. Table 1 enlists a few critical studies, the methodologies followed by the respective authors, and their limitations.

Table 1. Summary of Literature

S. No.	Authors	Year	Methodology	Limitation
1.	Krabbe, K. et al. [1]	1997	The authors presented their work on MRI using a diffusion-based technique to detect the skull's tumors. They used Apparent diffusion coefficients (ADC) as the basis of their study. They also suggested that if MRI and diffusion encoding are used, it can provide valuable results for detecting intracranial tumors.	
2.	Zhang, L. et al. [3]	2005	The authors presented their work on fMRI. The fMRIs deliver a 3D Brain image with respective intensity representations. Authors have given that Feature selection is the key to any classification. So, using fMRI images, the authors have inspected several machine learning-based feature selector algorithms and classifiers to serve the cause.	The computational time is very high. Intensive data pre-processing is required.
3.	Xuan, X. et al. [5]	2007	The authors analyzed the statical structure behind the brain tumor MRI and normal brain MRI images. The MRI images are first split into small parts from which characteristics are retrieved. Following that, machine-learning classification algorithms are employed.	Time efficiency is very low. A tremendous amount of dataset is required.
4.	Selvathi, D. et al. [7]	2009	The author did a comparative study over the general Fuzzy C-mean (FCM) algorithm and the modified FCM. The updated FCM method is based on the compression of the input data.	The computational time is very high.
5.	Jainy, S. et al. [9]	2012	The authors presented a work that aimed to create a method for multiclass categorization of brain tumors to aid in early detection. A dual-level neural network group is used in the system to categorize common areas and primary brain cancers such as astrocytoma and glioblastoma multiforme. They retrieved 218 intensity and texture characteristics from partitioned regions of interest and provided them as inputs.	A vast amount of data is required to gain good accuracy. A high GPU power system is required.
6.	Pan, Y. et al. [11]	2015	Three different methodologies are used for classification based on the grading process, and their results are compared. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classification with the help of SVM after feature detection. • Classification using Backpropagation Neural Network. • Convolutional Neural Network 	Additional feature detection needs to be done for SVM. The training sample size should be good enough for applying deep learning models.
7.	Machhale, K. et al. [12]	2015	The authors proposed a hybrid technique using SVM and KNN to classify abnormal and normal brain MRI images. The authors have successfully done a comparative study over the designed hybrid model. The steps followed are: RGB to greyscale	Quality maintained (high) dataset is required. High computational systems are required.

			conversion, filtering, and skull masking, Feature extraction, training, and testing using Classifier Model	
8.	Korfiatis, P. et al. [15]	2017	The authors have kept the classification criteria as only MGMT (deadly-primary brain tumor) or no tumor. For the classification, the comparative study is done over three residual neural networks (ResNet): ResNet 50, ResNet 34, and ResNet 18.	Extensive pre-processing is required.
9.	Mohsen, H. et al. [16]	2017	Firstly, MRIs were undergone through Image segmentation using Fuzzy C-means, then Feature extraction and reduction were done over resultant images using discrete wavelet transform (DWT) and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) techniques. Finally, the Deep Neural Network (DNN) classifier was fitted.	Extra step for extraction of features and reduction is required for classification using DNN.
10.	Yang, A. et al. [24]	2019	The author signifies that emphasis on the feature extraction from the medical images by applying efficient algorithms gives an upper hand to the medical professionals to identify the tumor accurately in less time and treat the patient as soon as possible. First local binary mode is implemented, then analyzed with the CNN algorithms. The model has an identification standard of 99.7% for massive datasets.	A considerable amount of dataset is required to achieve good accuracy. High GPU systems and storage are required.
11.	Mzoughi, H. et al. [30]	2020	A 3-D CNN model was developed and used over 3-D MRIs (augmented MRIs). It was tested on both manually generated 3-D MRI datasets and the already present one. The manual data was created using all three MRI types (T1, T1-contrast, and FLAIR).	High computational power is required. Only augmented data can be used for the implementation.

In 1997, K. Krabbe et al. [1] presented their work on MRI using a diffusion-based technique for detecting the tumors within the skull, while Lynn M. et al. [2] came up with their work on automatic tumor segmentation; in the year 2000. In the same decade, in 2005, Lei Zhang et al. [3] presented their work on fMRI (Functional Magnetic Resonance) images. In the year 2007, Xuan X. et al. [5] stated that the reformation in the central idea behind the research is the images are structural elements instead of the pixels because it has been challenging to find out that which tissue represents which pixel and which does not, in case one is only considering the pixels. In 2012, S. Jainy et al. [9] presented the use of CNN architecture and achieved great accuracy with the process. In 2015, Yuehao Pan et al. [11] proposed a study on the use of different methodologies for classification based on grading. They used SVM after feature detection, Back Propagation Neural Network, and CNN to serve the purpose. In 2017, Panagiotis Korfiatis et al. [15] came up with a comparative study of Residual Neural Networks. For this purpose, they used three types of ResNets (50, 34, 18). In 2020, Hao X. et al. [28] analyzed that image segmentation is vital for a medical professional with parameters such as position, size, and shape to give proper treatment on time and identify the tumor's correct location [6][8]. Figure 2 spun the research pattern observed decade-wise in this field. In 1990-2000, diffused encoding was used with MRIs, whereas the following decade witnessed the elevation in the FCM method using quantization and aggregation [10][13]. With the dawn of the decade 2010-2020, deep neural networks came into the picture, and the next decade will probably witness the exponential knowledge unearthing process using the latest advancements in machine learning, deep learning, and AI [14][17].

Figure 2: Research pattern (decade-wise)

3. Detailed Design

The detailed workflow diagram of the process followed is depicted in Figure 3. Image dataset, pre-processing, data segregation, and configuration of CNN are explained in sections 3.1 to 3.3. Section 3.4 gives the segmentation process for all three MRI types to identify the region of interest and 3D Volume configuration. After that, implementation and the results obtained are discussed in the following sections (Sections 4 & 5).

3.1 Image Dataset

The dataset is obtained from The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA). It is the official reserve for Cancer-related datasets of the National Cancer Institute, United States of America. The dataset of images used comprises Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scans of suspected brain tumor patients. All images are in Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) format with their metadata (Figure 4) which contains the basic information about the patient's diagnosis.

Figure 3: Workflow Diagram

Field Name	Tag	Content
▶ ReferencedImageSequence	0008,1140	1.2.840.10008.5.1.4.1.1.4\1.3.6.1.4.1.14519.5.2....9.7055.320230819474970716419167382910
PatientsName	0010,0010	PGBM-001
PatientID	0010,0020	PGBM-001
PatientsBirthDate	0010,0030	
PatientsSex	0010,0040	M
PatientsAge	0010,1010	052Y
PatientsWeight	0010,1030	170.5507528152
PatientIdentityRemoved	0012,0062	YES
DeidentificationMethod	0012,0063	Per DICOM PS 3.15 AnnexE. Details in 0012,0064
▶ DeidentificationMethodCodeSequence	0012,0064	113100\DCM\Basic Application Confidentialit...Option\113111\DCM\Retain Safe Private Option

Figure 4: MRI Metadata

3.2 Data Pre-Processing & Data Segregation

The following steps are followed to clean or pre-process the data and then segment it into two classes:

- ✓ Step 1: Initially, the dataset consists of multiple MRIs of each subject; many were duplicates, blurred, or contained noise. So, these images are eliminated from the data as a part of data cleaning.
- ✓ Step 2: As we are developing a CNN that can classify whether the subject is suffering from a tumor or not. So, we decided to segregate our data on whether a patient has a tumor or not.
- ✓ Step 3: Every MRI image has its metadata. By utilizing the DICOM file viewer and analyzing the metadata, we determined the presence of a tumor or not.
- ✓ Step 4: For cured patients, pixel representation is taken as "1," and the patients having tumors are represented as "0".

So, finally, our dataset has classified MRI scans based on two main classes, namely-

- No - no tumor, encoded as 0.
- Yes - tumor, encoded as 1.

3.3 CNN Configuration

The CNN model is configured, in which the input layer accepts MRI Images of size 224x224 pixels. The images need to pass through three convolutional layers and three Pooling layers. After that, the ReLu layer is present, where an activation function is used to remove all negative values, and finally, it gets connected to a fully connected layer that results in the output layer.

Figure 5. Basic Design of CNN

CNN has a layered form of structure, as depicted in Figure 5. It consists of:

- ✓ **Input layer**
It consists of image data represented by a three-dimensional matrix reshaped into a single column to feed in as input.
- ✓ **Multiple hidden layers**
 - Convolutional Layer:** In this layer, the dot product between the receptive field (a local region of the input image) and the filter takes place to extract features. It helps the machine learn the specific characteristics of an image.
 - ReLU Layer and Pooling Layer:** In this layer, the ReLu activation function (Rectified Linear Unit) is applied, and then max pooling is done by assigning maximum value to reduce the spatial volume of an input image.
 - Flattening Layer:** It transforms a 2-D matrix of features into a vector that can be fed into a neural network.
 - Fully Connected Layer:** It connects neurons of one layer to another layer and helps classify images among different categories by training. Here the process of feeding flattened images into a neural network takes place. (These are referred to as hidden layers because their inputs and outputs are masked, also called feature extractor layers)
- ✓ **An output layer** (classification layer)

3.4 Configuring Segmentation for different MRI Images

Segmentation is performed using various image processing techniques to obtain the regions of interest in the MRIs specific to the disorders.

3.4.1 T1-weighted MRIs

Figure 6 picturizes the steps for segmenting T1-weighted MRIs in chronological order.

- ✓ **Load Image:** The DCM (Dicom) format images are loaded in the TCIA dataset's directory.
- ✓ **JPEG Conversion:** The DICOM (DCM) images are being converted to JPEG (JPG) format so that image processing libraries (like open-cv) can access them.
- ✓ **Gray scaling:** The JPEG images of Brain MRIs are converted to grayscale images.
- ✓ **Thresholding:** On these images, thresholding is applied with a threshold value of 155px (0- black, 255- white).
- ✓ **Inverse Thresholding:** In this step, the inverse of the above step is done with the same value (155 px) as the reference.
- ✓ **Structuring:** The morphological transformations get initiated in this particular step. The structuring element (kernel) decides the nature of the operation to be applied to the image.
- ✓ **Morphology:** Two basic morphological operators (Erosion and Dilation) are used to perform the required morphological operations on the image.
 - **Erode:** It erodes the foreground object's borders. The kernel moves through the picture, and a pixel in the original image is replaced (1 or 0). It is only regarded as '1' if all of the pixels under the kernel are '1'; otherwise, it is eroded (changed to '0'). As a result, depending on the size of the kernel, any pixels along the border will be eliminated.
 - **Dilate:** It's merely the inverse of erosion. In this case, a pixel element is '1' if at least one pixel under the kernel is '1'. To remove noise, erosion is followed by dilation. It is also helpful in reassembling damaged components of an item (specific regions of disorders in our case). Also, closing is performed to fill small holes inside the foreground objects (disorder

region).

- ✓ **Mask Generation:** The BITWISE AND operation is applied to the image and mask generated by thresholding.
- ✓ **Edge and Contour detection:** The edge-detection-based segmentation technique, followed by contour detection (detecting the surface boundary line of the region of interest), was done to achieve the required result.

Figure 6. Segmentation Flow chart for T1 MRIs

3.4.2 T2-weighted MRIs

Figure 7 picturizes the steps for segmenting T2-weighted MRIs in chronological order.

Figure 7. Segmentation Flow chart for T2 MRIs

- ✓ **Load Image:** The DCM format images are loaded in the TCIA dataset's directory.
- ✓ **JPEG Conversion:** The DCM images are converted to JPEG (JPG) format so image processing libraries (like open-cv) can access them.
- ✓ **Gray scaling:** The JPEG images of Brain MRIs are converted to grayscale images.
- ✓ **Edge detection and Smoothing:** On the grayscale image, edge detection is applied to detect the edges in T2-MRIs to make them a little highlighted, followed by smoothing to deal with noise created in just the previous step (edge detection).
- ✓ **Thresholding:** On these images, thresholding is applied with a threshold value of 110px (0- black, 255- white).
- ✓ **Inverse Thresholding:** In this step, the inverse of the above step is done with the same value (110 px) as the reference.
- ✓ **Structuring:** The morphological transformations get initiated in this particular step. The structuring element (kernel)

- decides the nature of the operation to be applied to the image.
- ✓ **Morphology:** Two basic morphological operators (Erosion and Dilation) are used to perform the required morphological operations on the image.
 - **Erode:** It erodes the foreground object's borders. The kernel moves across the image, and a pixel in the original image (either 1 or 0) is regarded '1' only if all of the pixels under the kernel are '1'; otherwise, it is eroded (changed to '0'). As a result, depending on the kernel size, all pixels along the border will be eliminated.
 - **Dilate:** It's merely the inverse of erosion. In this case, a pixel element is '1' if at least one pixel under the kernel is '1'. To remove noise, erosion is followed by dilation. It is also helpful in reassembling damaged components of an item (specific regions of disorders in our case). Also, closing is performed to fill small holes inside the foreground objects (disorder region).
- ✓ **Mask Generation:** The BITWISE AND operation is applied to the image and mask generated by thresholding.
- ✓ **Edge and Contour detection:** The edge-detection based segmentation technique, followed by the contour detection (detecting the surface boundary line of the region of interest), was done to achieve the required result.

3.4.3 FLAIR MRIs

Figure 8 picturizes the steps for segmenting T2-weighted MRIs in chronological order.

Figure 8. Segmentation Flow chart for FLAIR MRIs

- ✓ **Load Image:** The DCM format images are loaded in the TCIA dataset's directory.
- ✓ **JPEG Conversion:** The DICOM (DCM) images are being converted to JPEG (JPG) format so that image processing libraries (like open-cv) can access them.
- ✓ **Gray scaling:** The JPEG images of Brain MRIs are converted to grayscale images.
- ✓ **Gaussian Blurring:** We have applied gaussian blurring to blur the bright fluid on a grayscale image.
- ✓ **Thresholding:** Thresholding is applied with a threshold value of 130px (0- black, 255- white).
- ✓ **Inverse Thresholding:** In this step, the inverse of the above step is done with the same value (130 px) as the reference.
- ✓ **Structuring:** The morphological transformations get initiated in this particular step. The structuring element (kernel) decides the nature of the operation to be applied to the image.
- ✓ **Morphology:** Two basic morphological operators (Erosion and Dilation) are used to perform the required morphological operations on the image.
 - **Erode:** It erodes the foreground object's borders. The kernel moves across the picture, and a pixel in the original image (either 1 or 0) is deemed 1 only if all of the pixels under the kernel are also 1. Otherwise, the pixel is eroded (made 0). As a result, depending on the size of the kernel, any pixels along the border will be eliminated.
 - **Dilate:** It is essentially the inverse of erosion. In this case, a pixel element is '1' if at least one pixel under the kernel is '1'. Erosion is followed by dilation to perform the noise removal. It is also helpful in joining broken parts of an object (specific regions of disorders in our case). Also, closing is performed to fill small holes inside the foreground objects (disorder region).
- ✓ **Mask Generation:** The BITWISE AND operation is applied to the image and mask generated by thresholding.
- ✓ **Edge and Contour detection:** The edge-detection based segmentation technique, followed by the contour detection

(detecting the surface boundary line of the region of interest), was done to achieve the required result.

3.4.4 Configuring 3D Volume

Using all three types of MRIs – T1-weighted, T2-weighted, and FLAIR, a python slicer is applied to chop out all the slices in the three planes. These planes are the Axial Plane, Saggital Plane, and Coronal Plane (Figure 9). The 3D volume of MRIs is conducive for medical professionals to find out the disease and study the other aspects of the disease at a higher level of treatment.

Figure 9. Planes of 3D Volume

4. Implementation

As discussed in the prior section, the designed architecture for CNN (Figure 10) consists of three convolution layers, three pooling layers, and two fully connected layers. The input layer receives MRI pixel values images (224×224). The convolution layer computes the dot product of input values linked to local neurons. Following the convolution layer, the Max pooling layer downsamples the volume. The filter size of the Convolution layer is 3×3 , while the downsampling size of the Max-pooling layer is 2. In the architecture, they alternate three times (this architecture is considered best, after implying several experiments). Then the flattening layer converts the matrix form generated from the previous phase to vector form.

Figure 10. Designed Architecture for CNN

Further, there are two fully linked layers. The activation functions for both layers are the ReLu and Sigmoid functions, respectively (concluded after the experiment). Finally, the linked layer is fed to two output nodes (neurons), each delivering a probability value for the two-output classifications. The network is trained using the optimizer "adam" (adagrad + remsprop), which can handle sparse gradients and noise issues by changing the needed learning rate based on training. The class mode under consideration is "categorical," as output is categorized into two distinct groups. The model runs for ten epoch cycles, with twenty steps per epoch, a batch size of ten, and a goal size of 224×224 . (concluded after experiments). Table 2 summarizes all these features of the CNN architecture [25-27][29].

Table 2. Summary Table of CNN Architecture

Parameter	Optimized Selection
Activation Function	ReLu and Sigmoid
Optimizer	Adam (Adagrad + Rmsprop)
Number of epochs	10
Steps per epoch	20
Validation Steps	10
Batch size	10

After obtaining results from the CNN model, segmentation is carried out (discussed in the prior section) to identify the regions of interest for determining the disorders inside the brain. The detailed process is stepwise explained below:

Step 1: Initially, the DICOM format (dcm) file is extracted from the TCIA dataset consisting of MRIs of brain tumor progression. These files can be opened using the DICOM file viewer application.

Step 2: The DICOM images are converted to JPEG format (Figure 11) to make them compatible with applying image processing techniques.

Step 3: The JPEG image file of brain MRI is passed through the grayscale conversion process (Figure 12). For T2 MRIs, edge detection is applied over the grayscale image, followed by smoothing (Figure 13). On the other hand, for FLAIR MRIs, Gaussian blurring is used over the grayscale image (Figure 14).

Step 4: For T1 MRIs, thresholding is applied on the grayscale image with a threshold pixel value of 155px. On the other side, for T2 MRIs, thresholding is used on the smoothed image with a threshold pixel value of 110px. And for the FLAIR MRIs, thresholding is applied on the gaussian blurred image with a threshold pixel value of 130px (Figure 15).

Step 5: The inverse thresholding is applied to the images obtained after thresholding, keeping the same threshold value of 155px, 110px, and 130px as the reference for T1 MRIs, T2 MRIs, and FLAIR MRIs, respectively (Figure 16).

Step 6: The morphological transformations get initiated here. The structuring element (kernel) decides the nature of the operation to be applied to the image. The morphological operations (erode and dilate) are then applied to the image obtained in the previous step (Figure 17), and then the closed operator is used to fill the holes in the main subject (Figure 18).

Step 7: Bitwise AND operation is applied to the image, and the mask is generated by thresholding (Figure 19).

Step 8: The edge-detection based segmentation is applied over the generated mask (Figure 20).

Step 9: The contours detection then follows the edge detection for detecting surface boundary lines of the region of interest (Figure 21).

Figure 11. JPEG Conversion

T1 MRI

T2 MRI

FLAIR MRI

Figure 12. Gray Scaling

T2 MRI

Figure 13. Edge Detection followed by smoothing

FLAIR MRI

Figure 14. Gaussian Blurring

T1 MRI

T2 MRI

Figure 15. Thresholding

FLAIR MRI

T1 MRI

T2 MRI

Figure 16. Inverse Thresholding

FLAIR MRI

Figure 17. Structuring

Figure 18. Morphology

Figure 19. Mask Generation (bitwise AND operation)

Figure 20. Edge Detection

Figure 21. Contour Detection

After that, 3D Volume is generated, using all three types of MRIs, T1-weighted, T2-weighted, and the Flair MRIs; the steps followed are as given below:

Step 1: Load and read the dataset - Firstly, load the dataset comprising all three MRI types and visualize them to confirm the successful loading.

Step 2: Create a Slicer and generate the planes/plans - After successfully loading data, apply a slicer over the data (this will slice the data and find out all the possible aspects of data to configure all the possible views in all the three planes). Finally, generate the 3D plan structure for all three (Axial plan, Sagittal plan, and coronal plan) to locate the view (Figure 22).

Step 3: Display Slicers - Finally, display the slicers with the angle widgets to track the view of every plan/plane at different angles (Figure 23).

The various parameters and hyperparameters were tuned multiple times to achieve the classification results by the CNN model, as shown in Figure 24. The study was carried out in different phases to examine the progression of brain tumors (Figure 25).

Figure 22. Generation of plans and slicers

Figure 23. Slicers at all three plans

```

Found 253 images belonging to 2 classes.
Found 253 images belonging to 2 classes.
Epoch 1/10
20/20 [=====] - 3s 167ms/step - loss: 0.3627 - accuracy: 0.8446 - val_loss: 0.2688 - val_accuracy: 0.9100
Epoch 2/10
20/20 [=====] - 3s 167ms/step - loss: 0.2796 - accuracy: 0.8808 - val_loss: 0.2515 - val_accuracy: 0.9100
Epoch 3/10
20/20 [=====] - 3s 171ms/step - loss: 0.3102 - accuracy: 0.8860 - val_loss: 0.2830 - val_accuracy: 0.8800
Epoch 4/10
20/20 [=====] - 3s 175ms/step - loss: 0.3139 - accuracy: 0.8650 - val_loss: 0.2330 - val_accuracy: 0.9300
Epoch 5/10
20/20 [=====] - 3s 167ms/step - loss: 0.3805 - accuracy: 0.8549 - val_loss: 0.2599 - val_accuracy: 0.9300
Epoch 6/10
20/20 [=====] - 3s 161ms/step - loss: 0.3637 - accuracy: 0.8342 - val_loss: 0.1978 - val_accuracy: 0.9300
Epoch 7/10
20/20 [=====] - 3s 163ms/step - loss: 0.3220 - accuracy: 0.8860 - val_loss: 0.2937 - val_accuracy: 0.8600
Epoch 8/10
20/20 [=====] - 3s 166ms/step - loss: 0.3085 - accuracy: 0.8601 - val_loss: 0.2488 - val_accuracy: 0.8800
Epoch 9/10
20/20 [=====] - 3s 174ms/step - loss: 0.3296 - accuracy: 0.8238 - val_loss: 0.2498 - val_accuracy: 0.9000
Epoch 10/10
20/20 [=====] - 3s 174ms/step - loss: 0.3182 - accuracy: 0.8860 - val_loss: 0.2291 - val_accuracy: 0.9300
<tensorflow.python.keras.callbacks.History at 0x7fa0d39d9358>
    
```

Figure 24. Results obtained for CNN

Figure 25. Different Phases of Progression

5. Results and Analysis

The results obtained after applying the CNN model are depicted in Figure 26 and Figure 27, showing Model Loss and Model Accuracy, respectively. The overall accuracy of 93% is achieved. Figure 28 shows the original image for T1 weighted MRIs, and Figure 29 shows the segmented image obtained. Likewise, Figure 30 shows the original image for T2 weighted MRIs, and Figure 31 shows the segmented image obtained. Figure 32 and Figure 33 show the original and segmented images for FLAIR weighted MRIs, respectively. Figure 34 shows the analysis histogram for the spread of channels for T1 weighted MRIs. Similarly, Figure 35 and Figure 36 respectively show the analysis histogram for the spread of channels for T2 weighted MRIs and FLAIR weighted MRIs.

Figure 26. CNN Model Loss

Figure 27. CNN Model Accuracy

Figure 28. Original Image for T1-weighted MRIs

Figure 29. Segmented Image for T1-weighted MRIs

Figure 30. Original Image for T2-weighted MRIs

Figure 31. Segmented Image for T2-weighted MRIs

Figure 32. Original Image for FLAIR MRIs

Figure 33. Segmented Image for FLAIR MRIs

Figure 34. Spread of channels for T1-weighted MRIs

Figure 35. Spread of channels for T2-weighted MRIs

Figure 36. Spread of channels for FLAIR MRIs

5.1 Analysis and Discussion

The importance of using segmentation techniques over the other methods lies in the fact that segmentation is time efficient, needs less computation power, can be deployed on any standard system (without high power GPU), and can be used to identify any disorders present in the brain. In contrast, deep learning techniques such as Mask R-CNN provide more accurate results in the case of identifying the smaller regions of tumors. Table 3 details the comparative study of the results obtained from image segmentation.

Table 3. Comparative Analysis of different MRIs obtained from image segmentation

T1- weighted MRIs	T2- weighted MRIs	FLAIR MRIs
No extra steps were required for applying contour image segmentation compared to T2 and FLAIR MRIs.	Extra steps, like edge detection and smoothing, were required to apply contour image segmentation.	Extra steps, like Gaussian blurring, were required to apply contour image segmentation.
Channels in the histogram are densely overlapping and not clear.	Channels in the histogram are comparatively the lowest.	Channels in the histogram are low overlapping and tend to clear.
Able to detect only one potential disorder point.	Able to detect more than one potential disorder point.	Able to detect only one potential disorder point.

Based on the above comparative analysis, it is clear that T2-Weighted MRIs performed better than FLAIR Weighted MRIs. FLAIR Weighted MRIs performed better than T1 Weighted MRIs. Hence at initial, medical professionals may prefer T2-Weighted MRIs first. Since, at higher stages, medical professionals may need to go for a 3-D view, which equally likely requires all three types of MRIs, all these MRIs are crucial and irreplaceable for better treatment at the later stages of diseases. Table 4 presents the course of comparison where two approaches are compared. Among the two approaches, the first approach is the Residual Neural Network (ResNet), used by the researchers over different types of MRIs. On the other hand, the image segmentation-based technique is used in this study to deal with the same problem with 93% accuracy.

Table 4. Comparative analysis of the approaches

As per literature	This study
Three types of RNN (ResNet 50, 34, 18) are applied for three types of MRIs.	Three different contour segmentation models are applied for three types of MRIs
The model requires a vast dataset to achieve good results.	A vast dataset is not required as it can be operated over small datasets.
Extensive data pre-processing is required.	No special pre-processing is required.
Needs high computation power.	Needs less computation power.
It takes high computational time to process output.	Time-efficient approach.
Deployable only on limited systems having high GPU requirements.	Can be deployed on any regular/standard system (without high power GPU)

Both the approaches are performing best on their level, but ResNet has some drawbacks which have been nicely tackled by the image segmentation-based technique in this study.

6. Conclusion

The detailed analysis of brain disorders and tumors depicts all the advancements in Nextgen technologies in the field in the past years. Various researchers have proposed several methods and algorithms to simplify the procedure of detecting abnormalities in brain structure to save the time and life of the patient. This study has discussed various techniques (machine learning algorithms, deep learning techniques, and image processing methods) to achieve accurate and efficient results while treating patients. A comparative analysis of all the three types of MRIs used during this study was done, and the best MRI that can be used at the initial stage of treatment was found to be T2-weighted MRI. The study is authenticated with an overall accuracy of 93%. The observations of this study are that with each new technique and a large number of its real-time applications, the researchers continued to develop Neural Networks and enhanced the results. Also, this helped in understanding the different views of what has been achieved through the methods mentioned above and what more can be done in the field for improvement. The central insight gained is to architect such a model using tools like Neural Networks and image processing, which can improve the process and make it error free, smooth, fast and reliable for detecting and adequately identifying disordered brain regions.

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